

Supplementary Material for On the Suitability of Local-First Architecture From Web Application Developers’ Perspective

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1 Introduction

This document contains the supplementary materials for the paper “On the Suitability of Local-First Architecture From Web Application Developers’ Perspective”. The materials include a description of the literature review, a list of papers included, and the conceptual result, a description of the study participants, the interview protocol used, and a mapping of identified architectural concerns to interview participants.

The overall research process, summarised in Figure 1, consisted of a literature review and a semi-structured interview. The literature review was used to produce an understanding of local-first architecture and it resulted in a conceptual framework summarising the concept. The framework contributed to answering the first research question and informed the design of the interviews. Thematic analysis was used to formulate concerns and a set of informal scenarios related to these concerns. The concerns contributed to answering the first and second research questions. The scenario analysis contributed to answering the second research question.

Fig. 1. Overview of the research process.

2 Literature Review

The following references constitute the final set of articles included in the literature review after the search and screening process described in Section 2.1 of the main paper. In total, 17 publications were selected based on their relevance to the principles, implementation techniques, and challenges of local-first systems.

Reviewed Articles

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2.1 Local-first architectural traits

The literature indicates that local-first represents a significant shift from traditional web applications, which primarily rely on cloud-based resources and client-server architectures [7]. Instead of depending solely on remote servers, local-first applications prioritise storing and processing data primarily on users' devices, allowing instant interaction even when offline. The main motivation behind this shift is to improve user experience by prioritising performance, availability, and control [7, 6]. Local-first software is driven by a set of core principles that aim to fulfil the goals of reduced reliance on centralised processing and storage. Advances in decentralised technologies have made local-first applications more feasible. Applications with local-first traits are already in widespread use: companies like Figma [20] and Linear [2] have used these principles to enhance responsiveness and reliability.

2.2 Local-first conceptual framework

We categorised fundamental aspects of local-first found in the literature into a conceptual framework, shown in Figure 2. The framework serves to organise and contextualise the theoretical and technical foundations of local-first systems and offers a structured perspective on their implementation and impact. It also functioned as the basis for designing the interview protocol and the background for analysing the interview data.

Fig. 2. Conceptual Framework of Local-First Architecture.

Principles. The concept of local-first software is characterised by several key principles, as described by Kleppmann et al. [7]. First, it emphasises offline capability, meaning the application must remain usable and fully functional without a network connection. Second, it values low latency, where interactions are immediate because they do not rely on a round-trip to a server. Third, seamless synchronisation across devices ensures that users can work from multiple platforms without manual coordination. Finally, user control and data ownership are central as users should retain access to and authority over their data at all times.

These motivations arise in response to the limitations of cloud-dependent applications, which often struggle with network interruptions, server outages, and latency. By contrast, the local-first design promotes a model where the network is treated as an enhancement rather than a requirement.

Enablers. Certain key technologies act as enablers for the distributed design philosophy of local-first systems. On the client side, browser-based storage plays an essential role. Solutions such as IndexedDB [11], the Cache API [9], and modern local databases like SQLite compiled to WebAssembly [17] enable persistent storage and transactional guarantees. In combination with service workers, these

tools allow applications to load and operate offline, intercepting network requests and serving locally stored content. Newer APIs such as the File System Access API [10] further expand what is possible locally by providing secure access to the user’s file system, enabling desktop-like file handling within web applications.

Each client maintains an authoritative copy of the application state. Synchronisation and consistency are achieved through background communication between replicas [7, 1]. Synchronisation engines (e.g., [19]) manage the exchange of updates, resolve conflicts, and support real-time collaboration. Some engines also support partial replication [5, 12], which is important for performance and storage efficiency. Local-first thus reframes key challenges in distributed systems, such as data consistency, fault tolerance, and synchronisation, by relocating trust and control from the centre to the edge.

Conflict-resolution mechanisms are central building blocks in local-first systems as they allow independent updates of shared data while maintaining eventual consistency [15, 18]. Two key approaches are Conflict-Free Replicated Data Types (CRDTs) and Operational Transformation (OT). CRDTs are particularly effective in collaborative environments, as they resolve concurrent edits automatically and ensure that all changes merge predictably without requiring central coordination [15]. OT, on the other hand, is commonly used in real-time editors and focuses on preserving the user action intent during simultaneous edits [18]. While OT also supports collaborative interaction, it typically depends on a more centralised coordination model compared to CRDTs.

Benefits. There are several claimed benefits of local-first architectures. For end users, improved responsiveness is achieved when local data access eliminates network latency, leading to smoother and faster user experience and possibilities for enhanced productivity [7]. The offline-by-default functionality of local-first applications presents an advantage as access to data and services is independent of internet connectivity. Local-first also empowers users by putting data control and ownership in the hands of users and reducing the constraints of vendor lock-in [7, 6]. This architectural approach supports greater autonomy and aligns with growing concerns surrounding data privacy and sovereignty.

From a business perspective, local-first reduces cloud infrastructure costs, minimises reliance on remote servers, and allows organisations to lower operational expenses related to data storage, network bandwidth, and computing resources [16]. Developer productivity can be increased by a simplified application architecture, reduced backend infrastructure complexity, and eliminating the need for writing networking code, as synchronisation engines handle data consistency automatically [1]. In a technical sense, local-first gives new possibilities for application development by enabling computational workloads that were traditionally placed on centralised servers to be offloaded to client devices.

Challenges. Despite its advantages, local-first software faces several challenges. Application developers must navigate the inherent complexities and limitations

of distributed systems, such as the CAP theorem. Often, applications must prioritise availability and partition tolerance over strict consistency (e.g. [14]). Storage limitations on local devices imply that it is impossible to fully replicate large-scale datasets. Dynamic partial replication techniques to some extent mitigate this issue but introduce complexities in query execution, data retrieval, and data consistency. Additional implementation challenges concern the management of data to be replicated, dynamic updates based on user behaviour, and ensuring security in changing access conditions.

Data security and privacy present continuous challenges, as local-first applications must prevent unauthorised access to local data. Unlike centralised cloud services, local-first software relies on distributed security mechanisms, making encryption and access control critical concerns. Additionally, data longevity, a fundamental principle of pure local-first software, remains an unresolved issue.

In addition to technical constraints, local-first presents cultural and skill challenges, as few web developers are used to this architectural style. Existing tooling and infrastructure is generally built to favour cloud-based solutions, and many widely used development frameworks, data systems, and third-party services are designed for cloud-first architectures, while frameworks and tools for local-first development are still in their infancy.

3 Study participants

Table 1 lists the study participants. The seniority of the participants was determined based on their years of relevant work experience, with senior level being six years or more and mid-level being between three and six years. There were no participants with less work experience than three years, so no other categories were used.

Table 1. Overview of the interviewed participants, including their identifier (P1–P5), technical background, and level of seniority.

Participant	Technical background	Seniority
P1	Full stack developer	Mid-level
P2	Backend oriented full stack developer	Senior
P3	Frontend developer	Senior
P4	Full stack developer	Senior
P5	Full stack developer	Senior

4 Interview protocol

The interviews followed a semi-structured approach to gather developers’ perspectives on adopting a local-first software architecture. Although the discussion

topics were predefined, the format allowed flexibility for participants to freely bring up issues and explore topics in more detail when relevant. There were no right or wrong answers, and the interviewer refrained from judging or addressing concerns during the session, focusing instead on capturing open and honest reflections. At the end, the interviewer provided a short summary if necessary.

Opening and Informal Conversation

The interview begins with brief small talk to create a relaxed atmosphere and establish open discussion.

Introduction to the Research Topic

Participants are given a short introduction to the research topic and the concept of local-first software. The explanation is based on the conceptual framework presented in this supplementary material. Key points included:

- The aim of the study: to examine whether a local-first architecture is suitable for a wider range of web applications or whether it still involves unresolved technical challenges.
- The core idea of local-first architecture: shifting primary responsibility for application logic and state to the user’s device, rather than relying on the traditional client–server model.
- The main user-facing benefit: improved responsiveness, as read and write operations occur against a local data store rather than over a network.
- Acknowledgement that the architecture also introduces challenges that may affect its adoption.

Participants are informed that prior knowledge of local-first systems is not expected. The interview assumes the availability of tools for local data storage and synchronization, though any concerns related to synchronization mechanisms remain relevant to the study.

Purpose and Interview Setting

The interviewer explains the purpose of the interview:

- To collect concerns (“developer concerns”) related to adopting a local-first architecture.
- To use these concerns as input for constructing scenarios later evaluated in the thesis.
- To focus on the participant’s experience with traditional client–server systems and how a shift toward a local-first model might affect such systems.

Main Interview Questions

Participants are first asked to reflect on a hypothetical situation:

- *“If you were required to migrate a familiar existing system toward a local-first architecture, what kinds of problems or concerns would this raise?”*

This prompt encourages participants to respond freely and identify issues based on their professional experience. To support reflection and ensure broad coverage of potential issues, the interviewer introduces prompts based on common software quality attributes. For each attribute, participants are asked whether adopting a local-first approach might introduce concerns or uncertainties. The attributes include:

- Security
- Usability
- Performance
- Availability
- Maintainability (introduced when relevant)

These prompts are not asked as strict questions but serve as conversational anchors if the discussion needs direction.

Closing the Interview

The interview concludes with:

- An opportunity for the participant to add any additional thoughts or concerns.
- A short recap, during which the interviewer can clarify earlier comments or connect concerns to the broader research context.
- Thanks for participation.

5 Data analysis and results

5.1 Analysis examples

The following examples illustrate how themes were formed in the analysis of interview data.

5.2 Mapping of identified concerns to participants

Table 3 shows which concerns were mentioned by which interview participants.

5.3 Formulation of Concern-Based Scenarios

To evaluate the practical relevance of the concerns, four representative scenarios were formulated. Each scenario addresses multiple concerns where current solutions remain partial, fragile, or context-dependent.

Table 2. Examples of thematic analysis. Underlined text designates identification of important information in the transcript.

Interview quote	Reflexive observations	Theme
“[...] if the sync between local data and server is <u>just a sync</u> , questions arise from a security perspective [...] how can we ensure the <u>legitimacy of the data?</u> ”	“Just a sync” implies no checks of data between client and server. “Legitimacy of data” means that the absence of checks invalidates any assumptions about the data. Any client could overwrite data on the server, which then propagates to other clients. A malicious server can push arbitrary data to a client. The concern arises because this is not desired.	Preventing client-side data manipulation from breaking consistency (C4)
“[...] if the business logic resides on the client, it <u>works well when there is only one client</u> [but risks multiply in systems with multiple clients or distributed logic].”	When business logic is in one place, it is clear where the responsibilities and risks are located. However, if business logic can be executed in multiple places, the risk arises that a malicious client can present results that are not in accordance with the intended constraints.	Preventing users from bypassing business logic and security checks (C8)

Table 3. Mapping of identified concerns to interview participants.

Concern	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5
C1: Not everything can be synced to the client	×				
C2: Triggering side effects			×	×	
C3: Accessing third-party services securely	×				
C4: Preventing client-side data manipulation from breaking consistency		×			×
C5: Keeping local and remote database schemas in sync	×	×	×	×	×
C6: Deciding what business logic belongs on the client vs. the server			×		×
C7: Risk of forgotten or incomplete security rules leading to vulnerabilities		×			
C8: Preventing users from bypassing business logic and security checks		×	×	×	×
C9: Managing user permissions and enforcing role changes	×				
C10: Ensuring strong authentication without a traditional server API layer		×			×
C11: Validating, accepting and persisting offline operations when back online			×	×	×
C12: Debugging and error handling becoming more complex with local cache			×		
C13: Avoiding conflicts in business logic across different platforms or teams		×	×		
C14: Securely handling sensitive data on the client				×	×
C15: Ensuring client devices can handle computational load				×	
C16: Preserving correct order of operations when multiple users edit the same data				×	
C17: Triggering events based on operations without coupling all logic to mutations				×	

Scenario 1: Offline Mutations and Delayed Synchronisation. The user performs several data mutations while offline. After two weeks, the device reconnects and initiates synchronisation. Extended offline periods increase likelihood of remote state evolution, requiring reconciliation while preventing redundant side effects and preserving consistency. *Related concerns:* data availability limits (C1), validating offline operations (C11), preserving operation order (C16), device capability variance (C15), and triggering side effects (C2).

Scenario 2: Unauthorised Data Access Through Compromised Client. A technically skilled user manipulates the client to bypass controls and access unauthorised data, attempting to sync changes with the server. Since clients operate in untrusted environments, critical validations must occur server-side, as manipulated clients can forge operations unless enforcement is complete. *Related concerns:* preventing client manipulation (C4), bypassing security checks (C8), incomplete security rules (C7), sensitive client data (C14), and dynamic permissions (C9).

Scenario 3: Schema Evolution Affects Mutation Interpretation. A new application version introduces data model changes with new required fields and validation rules. Users with outdated clients make offline changes. Upon reconnection, some mutations no longer align with current schema. Older clients may submit outdated or invalid mutations, requiring rejection or reinterpretation to prevent silent data corruption. *Related concerns:* schema synchronisation (C5) and cross-platform logic conflicts (C13).

Scenario 4: Triggering Side Effects from Decentralised Operations. A user performs an operation offline that should trigger side effects (e.g., an email notification or external API call). In local-first architecture, the client lacks secure direct third-party service access. Upon synchronisation, a mechanism should ensure that side effects execute exactly once in the correct context. Local triggering raises security concerns; server-side triggering must detect operation intent post-synchronisation despite delays or reordering. *Related concerns:* triggering side effects (C2), accessing third-party services (C3), business logic placement (C6), authentication without API (C10), and decoupled event triggering (C17).

5.4 Scenario evaluation

Offline Mutations and Delayed Synchronisation (Scenario 1) Resolution strategies such as CRDTs and Operational Transformation enable local mutations with eventual consistency upon reconnection. However, extended offline periods introduce challenges beyond connectivity absence. Host environment policies may purge local data after an inactivity period, and browsers can trigger system-level interventions outside developer control [21], which should be taken into account.

Servers may reject mutations upon re-synchronisation due to schema changes, logical inconsistencies, or malicious behaviour. Properly designed systems using

synchronisation engines should accept legitimate client operations even after significant delays. Synchronisation failures often serve protective functions, preventing compromised data from corrupting shared state. Robust offline handling assumes local changes are valid by default when applications remain untampered, with synchronisation accommodating delay, tolerating temporary divergence, and resolving conflicts automatically. Graceful error handling and optional reconciliation interfaces preserve integrity without undermining user experience.

Unauthorised Data Access Through a Compromised Client (Scenario 2)

Client manipulation must be considered in threat models of local-first systems. Hybrid systems where mutations are validated both locally and server-side effectively mitigate this risk. In such models, while the client provides an immediate, latency-free interface for reads and writes, the server remains the authoritative source of truth. This hybrid approach combines the responsiveness of local-first design with the integrity guarantees of traditional client-server validation.

In domains like data visualisation or note-taking, client manipulation risk is minor. Basic synchronisation safeguards prevent harmful data from reaching remote databases, maintaining system integrity. However, applications enforcing critical business rules require the “never trust the client” principle. Current tooling demands essential business logic be server-side to maintain consistent, secure behaviour despite client manipulation.

Purely local-first applications without centralised servers operate under different trust models. Users have full data control, including alteration through client code. Critical business logic should not be embedded in such systems unless accompanied by cryptographic verification, auditing, or reconciliation mechanisms. User data manipulation should be viewed as autonomy rather than a security concern; it is a feature of local-first software. Critical integrity constraints should be avoided or externalised, focusing instead on robustness, conflict resolution, and data coherence. Accepting user manipulation becomes philosophically consistent with local-first design principles.

Schema Evolution Affects Interpretation of Mutations (Scenario 3)

Schema evolution challenges arise when local-first systems must propagate remote schema changes to distributed clients, after being offline for extended periods using outdated schemas. Distributed, offline-capable storage requires co-existence of old and new schema versions with bidirectional transformations [8]. Without this support, schema mismatches cause data loss, corruption, or application logic failures.

Schema versioning maintains version identifiers on server and client. Upon mismatch detection, clients purge local state and resynchronise from server, ensuring consistency. This assumes networked servers and limits offline capability, requiring periodic reconnection. The *expand/migrate/contract* pattern [13] introduces new elements without disrupting functionality (expand phase), then removes deprecated elements after upgrade grace periods (contract phase). This

staged approach allows parallel operation of different versions during migration. An *append-only* schema model makes published schemas immutable. Developers stop using deprecated elements rather than deleting them, eliminating risks of breaking older clients or losing data. While this increases schema complexity, it ensures strong forward and backward compatibility for clients lagging behind server state indefinitely.

Each of these strategies trades flexibility, complexity, and robustness differently depending on offline usage patterns, inconsistency tolerance, and upgrade control. Current libraries provide schema migration mechanisms, enabling effective management through architectural design and transformation strategies.

Triggering Side Effects from Decentralised Operations (Scenario 4) In client-server models, side-effect operations such as sending email notifications or invoking external APIs are tightly coupled with server-side logic and executed within a trusted, synchronous context. In contrast, local-first systems decouple data mutations from immediate global coordination, complicating the orchestration of side effects that must occur exactly once and in a contextually appropriate manner. Side effects and third-party API integrations generally require server-side logic, conflicting with pure local-first principles. The design task becomes one of balancing local-first guarantees with minimal, auditable centralised components supporting necessary side effects.

The *authoritative server* model is particularly appropriate in scenarios where clients are expected to maintain connectivity to a central server most of the time. In this model, clients synchronise operations to a central backend that interprets them and executes side effects. Client and server need not implement identical mutation processing logic; local state updates on clients may trigger third-party API requests on servers. Servers ensure exactly-once side effect execution in controlled environments while preserving offline-first functionality and local responsiveness, though this reintroduces centralisation. This approach, called client-side prediction, is widely used in video games [3].

Event sourcing, on the other hand, records all client operations as immutable events in append-only logs [4]. This approach is particularly useful when the backend should not replay or recompute all mutations, yet certain changes in the data must still trigger additional logic. Side effects trigger in response to events during log replay or through dedicated effect processors consuming converged event streams. Relational databases may define triggers responding to synchronised event insertions by invoking server-side logic for external API calls or notifications. This reduces duplication risk and enables partial decentralisation, though increasing complexity and coordination challenges.

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